

Speculation on Gibbs' Paradox Part 2

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The Sackur-Tetrode formula for entropy of an ideal gas is designed such that the entropy for a gas with N particles, temperature T in V is the same entropy as the sum of two ideal gases in two containers with $N/2$, T and $V/2$ applying to each. In such a case, the pressure is the same in each of the two containers and the V one. The same summation (extensivity) holds for three containers with $V/3$, $N/3$, T etc. The summation, however, does not hold for $V/2$, $N/3$ and $V/2$, $2N/3$ with both having the same T . In such a case, the pressure is not the same in each box and both differ from the V one.

We suggest that these Sackur-Tetrode results seem to be unusual for the following reasons. First, any situation in which a known number of particles is constrained to a small volume and then allowed to expand into a bigger one without any T changes or work should suggest a loss in location (volume) information. This is what happens when an ideal gas irreversibly expands into a larger overall container when a holding wall is removed. It is not clear why that would not be the case for the two $N/2$, $V/2$ situations even if the ideal gases are identical. The second argument is based on the macrostates. In a gas with N particles in V , one can have a macrostate in which all of the N particles are sitting to the right. This is not possible in the two $N/2$, $V/2$ cases. As a result, there are many more macrostates in the V scenario which means more entropy. As a result, it is not clear why the Sackur-Tetrode equation is designed such that the entropy sum of the $V/2$, $N/2$ yields the N , V case.

We suggest that if one has two $V/2$, $N/2$ gases separated by a wall and the wall opens, then entropy increases. If one reinserts the wall, one has no idea how many particles end up on each side. One must statistically consider every possible case and this leads to every macrostate in V mapping to the product of macrostates in $V/2$, $V/2$ because one does not need to have $N/2$ in each $V/2$. Thus, entropy remains the same and there is no Gibbs paradox. If one decides to measure each $V/2$ and finds the same T and $N/2$ in each, then there is lower entropy than in the V case, but a measurement has been made which yields information and so entropy should decrease. If one does not measure the number of particles, the total number of macrostates in V and in the $V/2$, $V/2$ system is the same as argued in Part 1.

We note, however, that the tradition in physics is to make two $V/2$, $N/2$, T systems have the same summed entropy as N , V , T , i.e. the Sackur-Tetrode equation.

We realize that our description differs from that of traditional statistical mechanics (i.e. we do not have extensivity of entropy for V , N , T and two $N/2$, $V/2$, T boxes), but we suggest that it is interesting to consider.

Sackur-Tetrode Equation

The Gibbs' Paradox seems to be linked to the idea that without a special function of N added to the ideal gas entropy, placing a wall in the middle of a box of size V with N particles and temperature T to create two boxes with $N/2$, $V/2$, T , would lead to a decrease in entropy. Thus, a special function of N is added to create the Sackur-Tetrode equation (1):

$$S/N = \ln(V/N) + \frac{3}{2} \ln(T) + \frac{5}{2} \quad ((1))$$

One may see that if one creates boxes with the same pressure and T as the original V box, and sums entropies, they add to that of the V box. Such, however, is not the case for a box with T, V/2, N/3 and T, V/2, 2N/3. The pressures are different on each side, but physically one may have a holding wall between the two and remove it and then obtain N, V, T. In such a case, entropy is not extensive.

$$S = N \ln(V/N) + N \cdot C \quad \text{versus} \quad \frac{N}{3} \ln(3V/2N) + \frac{2N}{3} \ln(3V/4N) + C \cdot N = N \ln(V/N) + \frac{N}{3} \ln(27/32) + C \cdot N \quad ((2))$$

We suggest that from the point of view of macrostates and information, it seems strange that the sum of entropy of two V/2, N/2, T boxes equals that of a single box with T, N, V.

Information Argument

Qualitatively, entropy should define how much lack of information is present. If one has constraints holding N/2 particles in V/2 in two boxes, this gives more precise information about the location of these specific N/2 particles in the two V/2's than when the intermediate wall is removed and any particle can be found in V. This seems to be the same as two irreversible gases in a small container moving into a larger one case. There, T, N and total energy remain the same, but entropy increases. It is not clear why that should not be the case for the two N/2, V/2, T boxes.

Macrostate Argument

According to Boltzmann, entropy is -k multiplied by the ln of the number of macrostates. A macrostate in V can include all N particles being on the left or right hand side, but such a macrostate cannot be made from the product of macrostates of two T, V/2, N/2 boxes. Thus, there are fewer macrostates in the two V/2, T, N/2 boxes than in the V box, we argue and so V should have a larger entropy.

We only focus on volume because the term related to energy/temperature in S is $N \ln(T)$ which is the same for N, V, T and any set of boxes with a total of N particles and all having the same T.

Scenario

We consider two N/2, T, V/2 boxes side by side. We remove the adjoining wall and obtain a gas with N, T, V and more entropy as this is an irreversible process. There are now many more possible macrostates including ones with more particles on the right than on the left. We then put the wall back and argue, as in Part 1, that entropy remains the same because the number of possible macrostates in V is the same as the product of macrostates in the two N/2, V/2, T case. This is because each macrostate in V maps to the same one when one places the wall. The entropy is thus the same if T is the same in each box. This means that one has no idea how

many particles are in each box. This lack of information of particle number in each box increases entropy.

If one decides to count the number of particles in one of the two boxes, one might find $N/2$ for example (or some other number). In such a case, the entropy changes because one has obtained information. One can no longer have equal entropy, but less, but it came at the price of the extra information. If one has a flipped coin, one has entropy $-.5 \ln(.5) - .5 \ln(.5)$, but if one makes a measurement of the coin and gains information about what face is up, one has entropy=0. Information about a state which removes uncertainty (like the counting of particles) changes entropy, we argue.

The scenario we have given above differs from the traditional statistical mechanics, but we suggest that it is interesting to consider.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Sackur-Tetrode equation is adjusted by a function of N so that the entropy of an ideal gas with V, N, T is the same as the sum of entropies of two boxes with $N/2, T, V/2$. It is also the same as the sum of any size set of boxes with the same T and pressure such that $\sum_i N_i = N$. It is, however, not the same if the pressures are different. For example, $V/2, T, N/3$ and $V/2, T, 2N/3$ does not have the same entropy as N, V, T . There is no extensivity in that case.

We suggest that the Sackur-Tetrode result may be unusual from the point of view of information and macrostates. In the case of information, two boxes with $N/2, T, V/2$ constrain these $N/2$ particles to a smaller spatial realm and this means more information about location and hence less entropy. Removing the constraint means that any particle may now be found in V . This means more spatial uncertainty and hence more entropy, we argue. From the point of view of macrostates, removing the $V/2$ restriction means that one may have any number of particles (up to N) on the left or right hand side of V in a particular macrostate. This means more macrostates and hence more entropy.

The Gibbs' paradox arose by considering the entropy of V, T, N and placing a wall in the middle. It was assumed that there would be $N/2$ particles in each $V/2$ with T , but this requires a measurement as argued in Part 1 which changes entropy. If one places the wall in the middle, one has no idea how many particles are in each box and the entropy does not change hence there is no reason to add a special function of N to force the entropy of $N/2, V/2, T$ (two boxes) to sum to that of V, N, T , we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation